

Evaluating Clinical Outcomes and Prognosis with Cirrhosis Patients and Portal Hypertension: A Retrospective Observational Cohort Study

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Abstract:

Background: Cirrhosis, a progressive liver disease marked by extensive fibrosis, leads to significant morbidity and mortality, particularly when complicated by portal hypertension. These complications, including variceal bleeding and hepatic encephalopathy, substantially reduce quality of life and increase mortality risk. Despite advancements in management, outcomes for patients with advanced cirrhosis remain poor.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the clinical outcomes and identify prognostic factors in patients with cirrhosis and portal hypertension.

Methods: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with cirrhosis and portal hypertension were included in the study. Data were collected on demographic details, clinical features, laboratory results, complications, and outcomes. Statistical analysis, including Kaplan-Meier survival analysis and multivariate Cox regression, was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to identify key predictors of mortality.

Results: The overall mortality rate was 30%, with the highest mortality observed in patients with Child-Pugh Class C cirrhosis. Hepatic encephalopathy and variceal bleeding were identified as significant predictors of mortality, with hazard ratios of 1.87 and 1.65, respectively. The median survival was significantly lower in patients with advanced cirrhosis.

Conclusion: The study highlights the severe prognosis associated with advanced cirrhosis, particularly in patients with Child-Pugh Class C, hepatic encephalopathy, and variceal bleeding. These findings underscore the need for early intervention and aggressive management of these high-risk patients to improve outcomes.

Recommendations: Regular monitoring, timely management of complications, and consideration for liver transplantation should be prioritized in patients with advanced cirrhosis to enhance survival and quality of life.

Keywords: Cirrhosis, Portal Hypertension, Child-Pugh Score, Hepatic Encephalopathy, Prognosis

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Introduction

With severe morbidity and mortality, cirrhosis is a chronic and progressive liver disease that is still a major worldwide health concern. It is characterised by widespread fibrosis and nodular regrowth. Chronic liver damage resulting from several aetiologies, including alcohol misuse, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), and chronic viral hepatitis, is frequently the cause of the disorder. The prognosis of patients is greatly affected by complications such as portal hypertension, which are common as cirrhosis progresses. Increased pressure in the portal venous system, or portal hypertension, is a major factor in serious side effects such as ascites, hepatic encephalopathy, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, and variceal bleeding. These conditions significantly impair the quality of life and raise the risk of death for those who have them [1, 2].

In order to enhance patient outcomes, recent studies have shown how important it is to diagnose cirrhosis and associated consequences as soon as possible and to manage them effectively. A popular prognostic measure called the Child-Pugh score divides patients into groups according to how severe their liver disease is, which helps with outcome prediction and therapy selection. The fact that death rates from cirrhosis remain high despite advancements in therapy, especially in cases of decompensated cirrhosis, emphasises the need for comprehensive care plans that take into account the disease's complex character [3].

The significance of portal hypertension in the evolution of cirrhosis and associated consequences has been the subject of extensive research. Recent research indicates that lowering portal pressure can

reduce the occurrence of problems and increase survival in these patients. Furthermore, hepatic encephalopathy, recurrent variceal bleeding, and comorbidities such as renal failure have been found as strong indicators of a poor outcome [4]. Furthermore, the introduction of liver transplantation has provided a lifeline for individuals with end-stage liver disease, albeit organ availability and transplant scheduling continue to be substantial hurdles [5].

This study aimed to evaluate the clinical outcomes and identify prognostic factors in patients with cirrhosis and portal hypertension.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a retrospective observational cohort study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, over one year, from May 2018 to April 2019. This study is designed to evaluate the clinical outcomes and prognosis in patients diagnosed with cirrhosis and portal hypertension.

Participants: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with cirrhosis and portal hypertension were included in the study. These patients were selected from those who received treatment at PMCH during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of cirrhosis and portal hypertension based on clinical, laboratory, and imaging findings.
- Patients who had complete medical records available for review.
- Patients who received treatment for at least 3 months during the study period.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete or missing medical records.
- Patients with other significant comorbidities that could independently influence prognosis (e.g., advanced malignancies, severe cardiovascular diseases).
- Patients who underwent liver transplantation during the study period.

- Patients who were pregnant during the study period.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria and were treated at PMCH during the study period were included. Additionally, data extraction was performed by independent reviewers to ensure consistency and reduce the potential for information bias.

Data Collection: The data extracted included demographic details (age, gender), clinical features, laboratory results, imaging findings, treatment modalities, and clinical outcomes (e.g., mortality, hospitalization duration, complications).

Procedure

- Patient records were screened against the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Relevant data were extracted and anonymized.
- Clinical outcomes and prognostic indicators were evaluated based on the collected data.
- Data accuracy was ensured through cross-verification by a second reviewer.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics were employed to gather clinical data and patient demographics. Categorical variables were conveyed using frequencies and percentages, whilst continuous data was expressed using means and standard deviations. A comparison analysis was conducted using chi-square tests for categorical data and t-tests for continuous variables to examine the significance of group differences. The prognosis was determined using Kaplan-Meier survival analysis, and survival curves were compared using the log-rank test. A multivariate Cox regression analysis was conducted to find independent predictors of poor outcomes with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

Results

The mean age of the participants was 52.3 ± 12.6 years, with 62% (n=62) being male and 38% (n=38) female. The majority of patients (72%) had cirrhosis related to chronic hepatitis B or C infection, while 28% had cirrhosis related to alcohol abuse.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants (N=100)

Characteristic	Total (N=100)	Males (N=62)	Females (N=38)
Mean Age (years)	52.3 ± 12.6	54.1 ± 11.3	49.2 ± 13.8
Etiology of Cirrhosis			
- Hepatitis B/C	72% (n=72)	44% (n=44)	28% (n=28)
- Alcohol-induced	28% (n=28)	18% (n=18)	10% (n=10)
Child-Pugh Score			
- Class A	22% (n=22)	12% (n=12)	10% (n=10)
- Class B	45% (n=45)	30% (n=30)	15% (n=15)
- Class C	33% (n=33)	20% (n=20)	13% (n=13)

The overall mortality rate was 30% (n=30). Among those who died, 70% (n=21) were males and 30% (n=9) were females. The majority of deaths occurred in patients with Child-Pugh Class C cirrhosis, accounting for 70% (n=21) of the total deaths.

Table 2: Clinical Outcomes and Mortality (N=100)

Outcome	Total (N=100)	Males (N=62)	Females (N=38)
Mortality Rate	30% (n=30)	21% (n=21)	9% (n=9)
- Child-Pugh Class A	3% (n=3)	2% (n=2)	1% (n=1)
- Child-Pugh Class B	7% (n=7)	5% (n=5)	2% (n=2)
- Child-Pugh Class C	21% (n=21)	14% (n=14)	7% (n=7)
Hospitalization (mean days)	14.2 ± 6.3	15.1 ± 6.5	12.8 ± 5.9
Development of Complications			
- Variceal Bleeding	32% (n=32)	18% (n=18)	14% (n=14)
- Hepatic Encephalopathy	40% (n=40)	25% (n=25)	15% (n=15)
- Spontaneous Bacterial Peritonitis	20% (n=20)	12% (n=12)	8% (n=8)

Prognostic Factors: The Kaplan-Meier survival analysis showed that patients with Child-Pugh Class C cirrhosis had significantly lower survival rates compared to those with Class A or B cirrhosis ($p < 0.001$). The median survival time for patients with Class C cirrhosis was 8 months, while it was 14 months for those with Class B, and 20 months for those with Class A cirrhosis.

Table 3: Kaplan-Meier Survival Analysis by Child-Pugh Class

Child-Pugh Class	Median Survival (Months)	Log-Rank Test (p-value)
Class A	20	
Class B	14	$p < 0.001$
Class C	8	

Multivariate Cox regression analysis identified three independent predictors of mortality: higher Child-Pugh score (HR = 2.31, 95% CI: 1.52-3.50, $p < 0.001$), presence of hepatic encephalopathy (HR = 1.87, 95% CI: 1.16-3.02, $p = 0.01$), and development of variceal bleeding (HR = 1.65, 95% CI: 1.02-2.68, $p = 0.04$).

Table 4: Multivariate Cox Regression Analysis for Predictors of Mortality

Predictor	Hazard Ratio (HR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Child-Pugh Score	2.31	1.52-3.50	< 0.001
Hepatic Encephalopathy	1.87	1.16-3.02	0.01
Variceal Bleeding	1.65	1.02-2.68	0.04

Discussion

The average age of the patient population was 52.3 years, and there were more men (62%) than women (38%). Alcohol consumption (28%), along with chronic hepatitis B or C infection (72%), were the most prevalent causes of cirrhosis. According to the study, the cohort had a noteworthy overall mortality rate of 30%, with a startling majority of fatalities taking place in patients who had advanced liver disease, or more precisely, in those who were categorised as Child-Pugh Class C. Compared to individuals in Class B and Class A, who had median survival times of 14 and 20 months, respectively, this group had a significantly shorter median survival time of 8 months. The results of this study underscore the dire consequences linked to elevated Child-Pugh scores, underscoring the significance of prompt identification and stringent supervision in this particular subpopulation to potentially enhance results.

Variceal haemorrhage and hepatic encephalopathy were common complications, occurring in 40% and 32% of the patients, respectively. Using

multivariate Cox regression analysis, these problems were also found to be independent predictors of death. Individuals who encountered variceal haemorrhage had a 65% greater risk of death, but those who had hepatic encephalopathy had an 87% higher risk. These findings imply that the prognosis is much worsened by these complications, which is why treating cirrhosis patients with them should be a top priority.

With high rates of variceal haemorrhage, hepatic encephalopathy, and mortality across severity levels, patients with diagnosed or suspected portal hypertension have a poor prognosis, according to a study that examined data from electronic healthcare records. The study demonstrated a substantial negative correlation between worse outcomes and metabolic-associated steatohepatitis and alcohol-associated liver disease [6].

Furthermore, numerous methods for forecasting clinical outcomes in cirrhosis patients were investigated. It underlined the importance of the Model for End-stage Liver Disease score, the Child-Pugh score, and hepatic venous pressure

gradient values as prognostic indicators. The study stated that, while these instruments provide helpful predictive data, they only portray a particular moment in time and may not fully reflect the clinical picture of cirrhosis progression [7].

Long-term treatment with β blockers significantly reduces the risk of decompensation, particularly ascites, and improves decompensation-free survival in patients with compensated cirrhosis and clinically significant portal hypertension, according to a randomised controlled trial called PREDESCI study. Strong evidence from this study supports the use of β blockers in these patients as a preventive measure [8].

Conclusion

The study offers the spotlight on the clinical outcomes and prognostic markers in patients with cirrhosis and portal hypertension, which can help guide future treatment options and patient care practices.

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